

EFFECT OF COATING ON GLASS-FIBRE FRCM SYSTEMS UNDER DIRECT TENSILE AND PULL-OUT TESTS

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ABSTRACT

In this study, dry and epoxy-coated glass-fiber FRCM systems coupled with cement, lime, or gypsum matrices are tested. To characterize matrix-textile bond behavior pull-out tests (TPT) with a pull-pull setup, and direct tensile tests (DTT) were implemented. For DTT, coating produces higher load values at the end of the linear-elastic phase and a further phase of a considerable increase in the bearing capacity with subsequent mortar fractures. Interface delamination has also been recorded. Cohesive Material Law (CML) back calibration provided a trilinear diagram with a softening branch for the dry textile and an elastic brittle diagram for the coated textile.

KEYWORDS

FRCM, epoxy coating, direct tensile test, textile pull-out test, cohesive material law.

INTRODUCTION

Fiber Reinforced Cementitious Matrix refers to a class of composite systems used to create external reinforcements for existing masonry or reinforced concrete structures. It consists of an inorganic matrix reinforced by a fiber open-mesh textile. Characterization tests on FRCM systems aim at defining, first, the mechanical properties of the composite constituents. Through the Direct Tensile Test, DTT, (ACI 2020; CNR 2018), the composite lamina response under tension is observed together with the matrix-textile interaction behavior, as reported in (Focacci et al. 2020; Focacci et al. 2022). The test can be implemented in various manners (Kim 2021), although clamped grip and clevis grip are suggested by (ACI 2020; CNR 2018), respectively. Composite-substrate and matrix-textile interaction are jointly under observation in the single lap bond test, SBT, also known as direct shear tests. Although the effect of substrate stiffness on the matrix-textile bond behavior is often considered marginal, and so neglected in several interpretation models, in, e.g. (CNR 2018), for every type of substrate application (R.C., brick or stone masonries) a dedicated campaign is indispensable.

In (D'Antino et al. 2017), a test set-up named textile pull-out test (TPT) is proposed and compared to the results of direct shear tests on the same FRCM system. The good agreement found suggests the possibility of employing TPT as complementary to the investigation of matrix-textile bond behavior, in particular, to retrieve the Cohesive Material Law by back calibration, (Focacci et al. 2017).

The wide variability of FRCM systems constituents, both matrices and textiles, determines several failure modes for each of the mentioned tests (Ascione et al. 2015; ACI 2020; CNR 2018). However, crucial for all systems is testing and interpreting the matrix-textile interaction behavior, which influences global response and works as a trigger for failure when it deteriorates.

Fiber coating can be applied to textiles of FRCM systems to improve their performance in terms of enhanced durability of fibers, providing protection against environmental degradation (e.g., against moisture penetration, chemical attack, and abrasion). Textile coating is often employed to increase matrix-textile bond strength, enabling full exploitation of the textile capacity, (Bompadre and Donnini 2021). In this way, load-bearing capacity improves. In (Dvorkin et al. 2013), SEM observations have shown that the application of the coating results in a unitary behavior among the carbon filaments within the multifilament structure. Coating also reduces empty spaces between mortar and filaments and produces a homogeneous outline of the multifilament. In this way, coating ensures that the load is distributed uniformly in the textile section, increasing the load-bearing capacity. In (Donnini et al.

2016), the effect of different types and amounts of organic coatings and the use of a quartz sand layer on carbon yarns in cement matrix are tested by direct tensile, pull-off and shear-bond double-lap tests. In parallel, SEM observations are reported to highlight that relative sliding between the filaments are inhibited if coating manages to completely imbue the multifilament promoting cohesion between the filaments. Dry and pre-impregnated carbon yarns are also analyzed in (Donnini et al. 2018) through experimental investigations and a variational FEM model. A comparison between the traditional method of coating and an innovative use of mineral powders bound via electromagnetic waves for glass textiles embedded in a mineral matrix has been studied in (Homoro et al. 2020) through tensile tests. Results have shown that the proposed innovative method produces better results, determining an increase in the stiffness of the response.

In this work, the effect of the epoxy resin coating of a glass textile was evaluated on the matrix-textile interface behavior considering three different types of matrices, i.e., cement, lime, and gypsum. Experimental results obtained by textile pull-out tests (TPT) and direct tensile tests (DTT) were analytically interpreted assuming a cohesive bond of the matrix-textile interface and solving the differential system of infinitesimal equilibrium. In particular, Cohesive Material Law (CML) back calibration from TPT results allowed to highlight how the coating substantially modifies the textile-matrix sliding mechanism, determining basically different CML for samples with coated and uncoated textiles.

EXPERIMENTAL CAMPAIGN

Materials and methods

Materials

The experimental campaign was carried out on three different types of mortars (cement, lime, and gypsum) coupled with glass fiber, either dry or epoxy coated. The textile consists of a balanced bi-directional mesh based on dry fiber bundles, whose density is equal to 220gr/m² with a yarn spacing of 12mm. The resin used to coat the fiber is a bi-component epoxy resin with low viscosity and a Young Modulus in traction of 1800MPa.

The three employed mortars are a commercially available premixed and fiber-reinforced cement mortar (herein indicated as C) with class M20 according to (EN 998-2) and a maximum dimension of grains of 1.4mm; a commercially available premixed dry lime mortar (herein indicated as L) with class M15 according to EN 998-2 and a maximum dimension of grains of 1mm; a commercially available gypsum mortar with a compression strength of 20MPa and a maximum dimension of grains of 0.2mm.

Test setups and samples

The following tests were carried out:

- **TPB**, three-point bending tests according to (EN-1015-11) on 160mmx40mmx40mm mortar specimens, three samples of six specimens each, i.e., cement, lime and gypsum (TPB-C-xx; TPB-L-xx; TPB-G-xx)
- **C**, compression tests on the stumps of TPB tests, three samples and twelve specimens each sample (C-C-xx; C-L-xx; C-G-xx) according to (EN-1015-11)
- **TT**, textile tensile tests on 300mmx60mm specimens, two samples and three specimens for the dry sample (TT-D-xx), and six specimens for the coated sample (TT-C-xx). Specimens were clamped for 50mm length into test press jaws with aluminum tabs and instrumented with a 50mm extensometer; the displacement rate was set at 0.5mm/min
- **TPT**, textile pull-out tests on 500mmx60mmx10mm composite lamina specimens with external textile gripping length equal to 150mm, (D'Antino et al., 2017), six samples (three mortars, Cement, Lime, Gypsum, and two textile, Dry and Coated types) of three specimens each (TPT-C-D; TPT-C-C; TPT-L-D; TPT-L-C; TPT-G-D; TPT-G-C), specimens were glued

to 3mm thick aluminum tabs designed to provide a clevis-type anchorage, tests were carried out in displacement control at 0.2mm/min

- **DTT**, direct tensile tests on 500mmx60mmx10mm composite lamina, six samples (three mortars, Cement, Lime, Gypsum, and two textile, Dry and Coated types) of three specimens each (DTT-C-D; DTT-C-C; DTT-L-D; DTT-L-C; DTT-G-D; DTT-G-C), specimens showed 125mm gripping length with 3mm thick aluminum tabs with clevis-type anchorage, tests were carried out in displacement control at 0.2mm/min

Figure 1: Test setups. From left to right: textile tensile test, textile pull-out test, direct tensile test

Test results

Results of characterization tests on mortars and textiles are reported in Table 1 through mean values and coefficients of variation (CV). σ is the tensile strength of mortars for TPB-X samples, the compressive strength of mortar for C-X samples, and the tensile strength of textiles for TT-X samples.

Table 1: results of characterization tests on mortars and textiles

Group	n	σ [MPa]		E [GPa]	
		mean	CV	mean	CV
TPB-C	6	6	0.11		
TPB-L	6	5	0.08		
TPB-G	6	6	0.04		
C-C	12	24	0.05		
C-L	12	17	0.04		
C-G	12	21	0.04		
TT-D	3	841	0.09	85.535	0.11
TT-C	3	1419	0.10	98.217	0.08

Results of TPT tests

The load-slip diagrams of the textile pull-out tests are reported in Figure 2, where the slip is the relative displacement between the fiber and the matrix. It is possible to observe that all the samples with dry textile clearly showed a deterioration of the cohesive law, due to the debonding of the textile from the embedding matrix. On the contrary, all the samples with coated textile showed a linear-elastic phase, after which a progressive delamination textile-matrix occurred, as could be observed through the lateral cracks that progressively opened. As expected, the coating enabled reaching higher load values at the end of the linear-elastic phase (Table 2).

The average loads of the dry cement sample (TPT-C-D) at the end of the linear-elastic phase, at the end of the softening phase, and the peak load are respectively: 397N (0.031 CV), 1081N (0.026 CV), 1135N (0.019 CV). The maximum exploitation factor of the textile strength, IF, which is evaluated as the ratio between the textile tensile stress attained at peak and the textile tensile strength is also considered to analyze test results; for the TPT-C-D sample is $IF=0.562$. The coated cement sample (TPT-C-C) reached an average peak load of 1890N (0.05 CV, $IF=0.555$) and an average load at the end of the elastic phase of 1200N (0.166 CV).

The average loads of the dry lime sample (TPT-L-D) at the end of the linear-elastic phase, at the end of the softening phase, and the peak load are respectively: 532N (0.143 CV), 840N (0.134 CV), 928N (0.068 CV), with maximum $IF=0.459$. The coated lime sample (TPT-L-C) reached an average peak load of 1613N (0.08 CV, $IF=0.473$) and an average load at the end of the elastic phase of 1106N (0.186 CV).

The average loads of the dry gypsum sample (TPT-G-D) at the end of the linear-elastic phase, at the end of the softening phase, and the peak load are respectively: 549N (0.134 CV), 1340N (0.058 CV), 1405N (0.059 CV), with maximum $IF=0.696$. The coated cement sample (TPT-G-C) reached an average peak load of 2699N (0.15 CV, $IF=0.792$) and an average load at the end of the elastic phase of 1208N (0.123 CV).

Table 2: Results of the textile pull-out tests through mean values and coefficients of variation (CV) of the load at the end of the linear-elastic phase (P_1), load at the end of the softening phase (P_2), peak load (P_3), and maximum exploitation factor of the textile strength (IF)

Group	n	Load at the end of the linear-elastic phase P_1 [N]		Load at the end of the softening phase P_2 [N]		Peak load P_3 [N]		Exploitation factor of the textile strength IF
		mean	CV	mean	CV	mean	CV	
TPT-C-D	3	397	0.031	1081	0.026	1135	0.019	0.562
TPT-C-C	3	1200	0.166			1890	0.5	0.555
TPT-L-D	3	532	0.143	840	0.134	928	0.068	0.459
TPT-L-C	3	1106	0.186			1613	0.08	0.473
TPT-G-D	3	549	0.134	1340	0.058	1405	0.059	0.696
TPT-G-C	3	1208	0.123			2699	0.15	0.792

Figure 2: Load-slip diagrams of the textile pull-out tests

Results of DTT tests

The load-slip diagrams of the direct tensile tests are reported in Figure 3, where the slip is evaluated as the relative displacement between the two grip ends. It is possible to observe that all the dry samples showed only one crack (always at the end of one of the gripped parts), after which the debonding process occurred. In these samples, the maximum load attained is the first crack load. On the contrary, the coated samples showed several cracks: six in the gypsum and ten in the lime and in the cement, the first one always occurred near one of the gripped parts. As expected, coating enabled reaching higher peak load values, but it also induced a fragile failure with the delamination of one of the gripped parts, which was observed at the end of the test.

The average load of the cement dry sample (DTT-C-D) at the end of the linear branch is 1518N (0.084 CV), while the peak load in the cracked phase is 992N (0.059 CV), and the corresponding stress on the fiber, whose area is equal to $60 \times 0.04 \text{ mm}^2$, is 413MPa. The coated sample (DTT-C-C) reached an average peak load of 1784N (0.06 CV) with a corresponding stress on the fiber equal to 743MPa. The first crack load is on average 800N (0.074 CV).

The average load of the lime dry sample (DTT-L-D) at the end of the linear branch is 1058N (0.109 CV), while the peak load in the cracked phase is 465N (0.062 CV) and the corresponding stress on the fiber is 194MPa. The coated sample (DTT-L-C) reached an average peak load of 1525N (0.11 CV) with a corresponding stress on the fiber equal to 635MPa. The first crack load is on average 1014N (0.079 CV).

The average peak load of the gypsum dry sample (DTT-G-D) at the end of the linear branch is 1292N (0.06 CV), while the peak load in the cracked phase is 1072N (0.01 CV) and the corresponding stress on the fiber is 446MPa. The coated gypsum sample (DTT-G-C) reached an average peak load of 2447N (0.08 CV) with a corresponding stress on the fiber equal to 1019MPa. The first crack load is on average 1130N (0.057 CV).

For the DTT, the textile coating provides (i) an increase in the fiber stress at the end of the cracked phase between 1.80 (cement) and 3.27 times (lime) compared to the stress level attained in the dry textile, and (ii) a deep change in the failure mode, with visible delamination of the matrix. For all the considered matrices, the dry textile configuration provides load levels in the TPT test which are never attained during the DTT test. This is greatly influenced by the crack position in DTTs (at the end of the grip) and by the reduced bond capacity that could be well tackled and analyzed due to the long bond length tested (500mm).

Table 3: Results of the direct tensile tests

Group	n	Load at the end of the linear branch [N]		Peak load in the cracked phase [N]		Peak stress in the cracked phase [MPa]	
		mean	CV	mean	CV	mean	CV
TPT-C-D	3	15118	0.084	992	0.059	413	0.059
TPT-C-C	3	800	0.074	1784	0.06	743	0.06
TPT-L-D	3	1058	0.109	456	0.062	194	0.062
TPT-L-C	3	1014	0.079	1525	0.11	635	0.11
TPT-G-D	3	1292	0.06	1072	0.01	446	0.01
TPT-G-C	3	1130	0.057	2447	0.08	1019	0.08

Figure 3: Load-slip diagrams of the direct tensile tests

MODELLING TEXTILE PULL-OUT TESTS

TPT and CML back calibration

As shown by the test results section, fiber coating deeply changes the global response of the system, improving bond capacity and stiffness. The load-slip diagrams of the TPT test are employed here to retrieve the CML identifying the load and slip values corresponding to the end of the linear elastic phase ($P_1; s_1$) and, if present, to the end of the linear softening phase ($P_2; s_2$). These values relate to the CML by imposing a balance between internal and external work, done, respectively, by the tensile stress in the textile on the strain increment and by the interface shear stress on the slip increment. The energy balance provides for the load, P_i , and corresponding slip, s_i :

$$P_i^2 = 2 \psi A_f E_f \Gamma_{F_i} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where, $i = 1; 2$, ψ, A_f, E_f are, respectively, textile bond perimeter, cross-section, and elasticity modulus, and Γ_{F_i} is the CML fracture energy, i.e., the area subtended by the CML evaluated up the slip, s_i , corresponding to P_i . For the coated fiber systems, a linear elastic brittle CML was considered, since after a linear elastic phase in the TPT load-slip diagram, textile-matrix delamination occurred. For the dry fiber layout, instead, a deterioration of the CML was clear as well as a short pre-peak frictional phase. Hence, a bi-linear CML followed by an ending frictional plateau was employed. Results of the CML back calibration are reported in Table 2. The trilinear CML for dry fiber shows the following form:

$$\tau(s(x)) = \begin{cases} \frac{\tau_1}{\delta_1} s(x) & ; 0 \leq s(x) \leq \delta_1 \\ \frac{\tau_1 - \tau_2}{\delta_1 - \delta_2} (s(x) - \delta_1) + \tau_1 & ; \delta_1 \leq s(x) \leq \delta_2 \\ \tau_2 & ; s(x) > \delta_2 \end{cases}$$

Eq. 2

For coated fiber, the brittle CML shows only the first branch of Eq. 2. Once fixed the CML, the global load-slip diagram referring to the TPT test can be predicted by solving the equilibrium condition over the infinitesimal length dx . In particular, the textile axial force increase, $E_f t_f b_f ds'(x)$, being $s'(x)$ textile strain, $s(x)$ matrix-textile slip, and b_f, t_f and E_f , respectively, textile width, equivalent thickness and elasticity modulus, is in equilibrium with the bond force, $\tau(s(x))\psi dx$, according to:

$$s''(x) = \psi (b_f E_f t_f)^{-1} \tau(s(x)) \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where, ψdx , is the bond surface per infinitesimal length, dx , with respect to the textile perimeter, $\psi = 2 b_f$. To solve Eq. 3 boundary conditions (BC) are set according to geometry of the problem, in this case $s'(0) = 0$, where $x = 0$ coincides with the unloaded end extremity, and the phase ruled by the branch of the CML. In the first phase, when the linear elastic branch has fully developed along the domain, the second BC to solve Eq. 3 is $s(L) = \delta_1$. In the elastic-softening phase, part of the jacket's interfaces are still ruled by the first branch of the CML, and part follows the second, hence, two forms of Eq. 3 are needed to find the full expression of slips along the domain and the selected four BCs are: $s_1'(0) = 0$; $s_1'(a) = s_2'(a)$; $s_1(a) = s_2(a)$; $s_2(L) = \delta_2$. The lower-case number refers to the portion of the domain in the linear phase or in the softening phase, and the coordinate at which the change occurs is named $x = a$. For the third phase, where all the three branches CML are active along the domain, two couples of continuity conditions are necessary at two distinct coordinates (Rovero et al. 2020; Misseri et al. 2021).

MODELING DIRECT TENSILE TESTS

DTT uncracked configuration

In the DTT composite lamina, matrix axial stiffness is, for the considered FRCM systems, much higher than that of the textile. Load is transferred to the matrix along grips and the matrix bears most part of the external load, while the textile is weakly tightened. Hence, matrix-textile slip can be assumed negligible, and the rule of admixtures can be straightforwardly employed to build the first branch of the global diagram, (Soranakom & Mobasher, 2010).

Figure 4: a) DTT uncracked and cracked configurations (one or two cracks, C1 and C2) identifying the Single and the Double Pull-out Layouts (SPL and DPL, respectively), b) textile and matrix force distribution along in the one crack configuration C1 to pass to C2

DTT Cracked configuration

Cracks can form in any cross-section free from grips, and each newly formed crack determines a different configuration of the reference domain (e.g., one-crack configuration – C1). According to test results, the first crack, caused by the attainment of the matrix tensile strength, has always occurred at the end of one of the grips, hence, this has been the first configuration considered.

For any crack configuration, one or more cross-sections of unbonded textile transfer load between crack-separated portions within a series of pull-out layouts. In each layout, the force in the textile diminishes moving apart from the crack mouth, according to the CML ruling the matrix-textile slip. In any cross-section of the layout, matrix force can be evaluated as the difference between the force in the textile at the crack mouth, and the force in the textile at the cross-section of interest; at crack mouths, force in the matrix is zero.

When the first crack has formed (one-crack configuration – C1), the two portions show the same layout, (Single Pull-out Layout - SPL, Figure 4a), with zero force in the textile at free ends and the same imposed load at the crack mouth, i.e., the boundary conditions that define SPL and provide the solution to Eq. 3. Independently from the first crack position, second crack forms (two-crack configuration – C2, Figure 4a), if can, at the grip end of the longest of the two portions, where matrix shows the maximum tensile load. Indeed, at the grip end cross-section, the textile load is lower in the longest portion than in the shortest, so the matrix load is greater since the force transferred by the textile at the crack mouths is the same, Figure 4b.

If a second crack could form (C2), the three portions show two different layouts, the two extremity portions have the same layout of the one-crack configuration (SPL). The central portion, Double Pull-out Layout – DPL, is symmetrically loaded and shows maximum imposed textile load at crack mouths and maximum matrix force in the middle, Figure 4a C2 configuration. Further cracks, (any-crack configuration) can form hence by successive halving of the central DPLs. Given the symmetry of DPL, half of it can be modeled, imposing assigned force at the crack mouth extremity and null slips in the symmetry section as in a fixed far-end layout, (Bertolli & D’Antino, 2022). These are the boundary conditions that define DPL and provide solution to Eq.3.

The load slip diagram of each configuration (C1, C2, Cn...), is built by summing attained slips of each layout (SPLs, DPLs) according to common textile force values. Indeed, SPLs and DPLs are linked one another by textile strain continuity (same force value in the textile at crack mouth) and each layout contributes to the crack mouth opening displacement according to layout and length. By reconnecting the load slip diagrams of different configurations, it is possible to represent the cracking process. Each configuration is built independently from another; then, the matrix crack load for each configuration is evaluated. Such a value represents the “end” of a configuration, so that load jumps, e.g., from C1 diagram to C2 diagram, can be defined.

Table 4: Reference values of the trilinear and brittle CML considered respectively for the dry (D) and coated (C) textiles, respectively, coupled to cement (C), lime (L), and gypsum (G) mortars

Group	Shear stress		slip	
	τ_1 [MPa]	τ_2 [MPa]	s_1 [mm]	s_2 [mm]
C-D	0.094	0.01	0.07	0.46
L-D	0.044	0.011	0.26	0.57
G-D	0.107	0.004	0.31	0.71
C-C	0.108	-	0.47	-
L-C	0.118	-	0.36	-
G-C	0.305	-	0.26	-

Results of the analytical interpretation

For the back calibration of the elastic brittle CML, the results of TPT are employed, and reference values are reported in Table 4. In Figure 5, red plots show the load slip diagram of the TPT tests, according to the CML values considered, and the brown solid hatch is the test results envelope. With black plots, Figure 5 also shows estimations of the DTT load–slip diagram (with slip, it is here intended the relative displacement between points at the end of the grips), and the grey solid hatch is the test results envelope.

Concerning DTT estimations, the cracked configurations and layout were assigned according to test results. For all the dry fiber samples, a single crack was considered placed at the end of the grip, at 120mm distance from the free end, hence, two SPLs were analyzed (125mm and 375mm long). Good agreement is found between experimental results and analytical estimations. It is worth noting that for the DTT-L-D (lime mortar and dry fiber) deterioration of the CML might have occurred after the crack formed, with consequent permanent slip after the matrix crack. Indeed, good agreement with experimental outcomes is found providing a shift of 0.3mm to the interpretation curve of the C1 configuration. For all the coated fiber samples, 5 or 6 cracks were considered. The final configurations are two 125mm-long SPLs, and four 62.5mm-long DPLs for C5, and two 125mm-long SPLs, three 62.5mm-long and two 31.25mm-long DPLs for C6.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, the results of an experimental campaign on dry and epoxy-coated glass-fiber FRCM systems are reported, each textile type is associated with cement, lime, or gypsum matrices. Both direct tensile and textile pull-out tests have been carried out. Test results show that fiber coating deeply altered the overall response of both the DTT and TPT tests, improving, in particular, the quality of the bond behavior. The improvement could be tackled by visual inspection during DTT since more cracks with reduced mouth opening displacement could form. Fiber coating proved effective in increasing shear peak capacity and associated slip in the CML, more markedly for the gypsum and lime-based mortars. Fiber coating also provided a deep change in failure mode after the linear elastic branch of the CML, in particular, from textile debonding to textile delamination, and consistently the CML representing the coated samples show a linear-brittle shape. To interpret DTT results, the back calibrated CML is exploited, and the observed crack pattern is considered in the analytical model through the use of different configurations (one-crack, two-crack, etc..). Each configuration, studied independently from the others and providing a branch of the load slip diagram, is composed of a series of one or two types of layouts. The layouts, which resemble every crack separated portion, foresee a single or double textile pull-out loading of the composite, respectively for ending portions or in-between ones. The different branches (for every configuration) of the load slip diagram are linked one another by the load jumps occurring at crack formation. Good agreement is found between analytical estimations and experimental results of DTT.

Figure 5: Results of the analytical interpretation of TPT (red plots), on which the CML has been calibrated, and DTT (black plots), superposed to the test diagrams envelopes (brown and grey solid hatches for TPT and DTT, respectively)

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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